

**TEACHERS' COMPETENCE AND ITS RELATIONSHIP TO THE RPMS-PPST
RESULTS OF SELECTED PUBLIC-SCHOOL TEACHERS: BASIS FOR A
PROPOSED TRAINING DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM**

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Teachers' Competence and its Relationship to the RPMS-PPST Results of Selected Public-School Teachers: Basis for a Proposed Training Development Program

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Abstract

This study aimed to assess the teachers' competence and its relationship to the RPMS-PPST results of selected public school teachers. It served as the basis for a training development program during the school year 2024-2025. Regarding classroom management, the teacher-respondents obtained a composite mean of 3.52, which was verbally interpreted as highly competent. In terms of Mastery of the Subjects, the teacher-respondents obtained a composite mean of 3.57, which was verbally interpreted as Highly Competent. In terms of Instructional Material Development, the teacher-respondents obtained a composite mean of 3.56, which was verbally interpreted as Highly Competent. In terms of Teaching Strategies and Approaches, the teacher-respondents obtained a composite mean of 3.61, which was verbally interpreted as Highly Competent. In terms of Communication Skills, the teacher-respondents obtained a composite mean of 3.56, which was verbally interpreted as Highly Competent. In terms of Learning Assessment and Reporting, the teacher-respondents obtained a composite mean of 3.68, which was verbally interpreted as Highly Competent. Out of the total cohort of 56 teachers evaluated, a significant majority, comprising 76.78% (43 teachers), achieved the highest rating of "Outstanding," with scores ranging from 4.1 to 5.00. This dominance at the top of the rating scale underscored a commendable level of instructional competence and commitment among the teaching staff. Conversely, 23.22% (13 teachers) of the evaluated staff were rated as "Very Satisfactory," reflecting a solid performance level that, while slightly below the top tier, still denoted commendable achievement and effective classroom management. This group of teachers exhibited a strong grasp of pedagogical techniques, student engagement strategies, and curriculum delivery, contributing positively to the overall educational experience despite not attaining the highest rating. The significant relationship between the level of perception of the teachers as regards their competence to the RPMS-PPST results and the teacher's performance based on their IPCRF. The significant relationship between the teachers' level of perception regarding their competence to the RPMS-PPST results and the teacher's performance based on their IPCRF is very evident and Highly Significant.

Keywords: *communication skills, IPCRF, RPMS-PPST*

Introduction

School leadership has a significant impact in fostering student achievement. The impact of leadership is greatest when it is focused on improving teaching and learning, and it is amplified when responsibilities for leading teaching and learning are widely distributed across the school.

One important component of school leadership is instructional leadership, which is a form of leadership that places teaching and learning at the forefront of school decision-making. It is an overarching orientation that gives structure to a school's direction. It is evidenced by core leadership practices and skills that support teaching and student outcomes and drive school improvement and sustained success.

Instructional coaches provide instructional support, from goal setting to teacher support and mentoring, assessment expertise, and professional development on topics such as effective instructional strategies, current research, and using data to inform instruction.

Instructional leadership, as the lead principal, school improvement workshop, November 2021) Describes, is a collaborative effort between the school leader and the school team. Together, they unpack the why and the how of the school's improvement agenda, whether it's related to curriculum or pedagogy. It's not about the leader being the sole expert, but about being a knowledgeable guide, walking alongside the school team as they learn together.

Instructional leaders, as per Hattie (2019), are primarily focused on students. They are responsible for ensuring that teachers and the school as a whole positively impact student learning and instructional issues. This involves conducting classroom observations, facilitating professional development that enhances student learning, and communicating and upholding high academic standards. They also ensure that all school environments are conducive to learning.

Instructional leadership is about setting those really good examples from the leadership team – so what I expect my staff to do, I do myself. It's very important that they see me with them out there in the community, alongside them in their teaching, talking with them, checking in with them – and if there is something that I ask them to do, I would expect myself to do that as well. So, it's working with teachers, alongside my staff, and ensuring they know I am in it with them – (Principal, school improvement workshop, November 2021).

On the other hand, coaching and mentoring of key teachers, such as Master Teachers, as a strategic intervention program for

professional and personal development, proved to promote positive relationships and the well-being of teachers. These master teachers are empowered and capacitated through the instructional leadership practices of the school principals.

According to Jones, Kelsey, & Brown (2020), both parties benefit from long-lasting benefits when a relationship is successful. In a study, agriculture mentors or cooperating teachers are one of the most important influences on the development of new teachers. Positive mentoring relationships and a wellness model demonstrated indirect benefits such as establishing a safe space, continuing relationships between mentees and mentors, networking benefits, campus acculturation, and a better understanding of organizational politics and their potential to impact faculty well-being positively.

Consequently, coaching and mentoring are critical for experienced teachers and school leaders. Mentoring can result in unintended consequences due to its dynamic nature and the fact that both mentor and mentee play critical roles in the mentoring process's success. (Mathipa & Matlabe, 2019). However, it is determined that mentoring and coaching are "not a panacea for educator well-being." Rather than that, the quality and effectiveness of the mentoring and coaching relationship are critical, and if negative experiences are left unattended, they may contribute to their stress and increased workload. (Hollweck, 2019). Negative coaching and mentoring can also harm teachers' well-being and teaching (Hollweck, 2019).

In consideration of the above-cited ideas, the researcher was urged to conduct this study on the public-school principals' instructional leadership practices to master teachers' competence in executing RPMS-PPST mentoring and coaching processes to determine the effectiveness of the instructional leadership practices implemented by the school principals; to determine if the master teachers can follow the RPMS-PPST prescribed standards, procedures, and processes in conducting coaching and mentoring with their teacher-mentees; and to propose an action plan that would strengthen the skills of both the school principal and teachers in instructional leadership and mentoring and coaching.

Research Questions

This study aimed to assess the teachers' competence and its relationship to the RPMS-PPST results of selected public-school teachers which served as basis for a training development program during the school year 2024-2025. More specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of perception of the teachers as regards their competence in relation to the RPMS-PPST results in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. classroom management;
 - 1.2. mastery of the subjects;
 - 1.3. instructional material development;
 - 1.4. teaching strategies and approaches;
 - 1.5. communication skills; and
 - 1.6. learning assessment and reporting?
2. What is the teachers' performance based on their IPCRF of SY 2023-2024?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of perception of the teachers as regards their competence in relation to the RPMS-PPST results and the teachers' performance based on their IPCRF?
4. Based on the results of the study, what training development program may be proposed?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive research design, a method that involves comprehensive data collection and analysis. As Siedlecki (2020) notes, this approach uses observations and case studies to provide a detailed and thorough picture of the issue under investigation. It ensures that the data collected explains the situation more completely and provides objectivity to current issues or problems. This method is particularly effective in ensuring the objectivity of the study's variables and in providing a comprehensive and clear picture of a group or situation.

The method primarily focuses on describing the nature of a demon "aph" c segment without focusing on "why" a particular phrase "omenon oc" yours. In other words, it "describes" the "res" arch subject without covering "why" it happens.

Therefore, the researcher will use descriptive research design to determine the school administrators' effectiveness in implementing school programs and projects.

Respondents

The researcher used stratified random sampling. This was conducted in the selected Antipolo City schools, specifically at Bagong Nayon II Elementary School. The study respondents were elementary school teachers. Each instrument was administered to all the respondents. The respondents were given enough time to answer the research instrument.

The scope of this study was comprehensive, encompassing teachers from a diverse range of schools in Antipolo City. This inclusivity

ensured that the research was representative of the broader educational landscape in the city.

Instrument

The study used a researcher-made questionnaire and descriptive questions that served as indicators in every variable. The survey questionnaire consisted of three parts. The first part contained the evaluation of the respondents. The second part contained the school performance rating, and the third part contained the comments and suggestions of the school administrator and teacher respondents.

The questionnaires, serving as the survey instrument of the study, underwent a rigorous validation process. This process involved a panel of experts, including principals, master teachers, English teachers, and an education program supervisor, who meticulously analyzed and scrutinized the contents of the questionnaire. Their comments and feedback were carefully considered in the final approval of the method, which was further examined by a consultant serving as the researcher's proofreader.

Procedure

Permission from the concerned authorities were sought before the conduct of the study. Upon approval of the Schools Division Superintendent and the principal, the questionnaire – checklists were administered to the teacher-respondents from the selected Elementary Schools in Antipolo City and were personally retrieved by the researcher.

Data Analysis

Frequency, Percentage Distribution, and Ranking. This was used to analyze and summarize the results of the responses from the questionnaire.

Pearson r Correlation. This was used to determine the significant relationship between the level of perception of the teachers as regards their competence in relation to the RPMS-PPST results and the teachers' performance based on their IPCRF.

Results and Discussion

This section provided the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the gathered data from the questionnaires answered by the respondents in accordance with the specific questions posited on the objectives of the study.

Level of perception of the teachers as regards their competence in relation to the RPMS-PPST results

Level of perception of the teachers as regards their competence in relation to the RPMS-PPST results in terms of Classroom Management

Table 1. *Level of perception of the teachers as regards their competence in relation to the RPMS-PPST results in terms of Classroom Management*

	<i>A. Classroom Management</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
<i>As a teacher, I...</i>				
1.	manage classroom structure to engage learners in a meaningful exploration discovery and hands-on activities within the range of physical learning environment.	3.48	Highly Competent	4
2.	manage learners' behavior constructively by applying positive and non-violent discipline.	3.35	Highly Competent	5
3.	use differentiated, developmentally appropriate learning experiences to address learners' gender, needs, strengths, interests, and experiences.	3.66	Highly Competent	1
4.	maintain safe and orderly classroom free from destructions.	3.64	Highly Competent	2
5.	establish routines and procedures to maximize instructional time.	3.48	Highly Competent	3
<i>Composite Mean</i>		3.52	Highly Competent	

As discussed in Table 1, the respondents stated that they use differentiated, developmentally appropriate learning experiences to address learners' gender, needs, strengths, interests, and experiences, which got the highest weighted mean of 3.66 and the highest rank of 1. The findings highlighted that administrators employed differentiated and developmentally appropriate learning experiences to cater to learners' diverse needs, strengths, interests, and experiences, including considerations of gender. Administrators were observed to adopt a personalized approach to education, recognizing the unique attributes and backgrounds of each student. This approach aimed to create inclusive and supportive learning environments where all learners could thrive. Teachers perceived these efforts as crucial in promoting equity and ensuring that educational experiences were meaningful and relevant to every student. By tailoring learning experiences based on individual characteristics, administrators demonstrated a commitment to addressing the holistic development of learners, fostering engagement, and enhancing overall educational outcomes. Predanocová et al. (2021) stated that ten essential teacher competencies, including the competence to develop a positive classroom climate, are crucial for effective education and training, affecting pupil personal and social development.

However, the said group of respondents stated that they manage learners' behavior constructively by applying positive and non-violent discipline which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.35 and least rank of 5. The findings revealed that administrators managed learners' behavior constructively by consistently applying positive and non-violent discipline methods. Administrators prioritized creating a

supportive and respectful school environment where discipline was approached as an opportunity for growth rather than punishment. This approach aimed to foster a positive school climate conducive to learning and personal development. Teachers perceived these practices as effective in promoting students' social-emotional well-being and in maintaining a conducive learning atmosphere. By emphasizing positive reinforcement and non-violent approaches, administrators demonstrated a commitment to nurturing students' behavior in a way that aligned with educational and ethical standards. This constructive management of behavior contributed to a cohesive and safe school community where students felt valued and supported in their educational journey. Keller-Schneider et al. (2020) stated that beginning teachers have lower sense of competence in professional requirements, but challenges vary across career stages, suggesting support for new teachers and promoting optimal resource use.

The composite mean of 3.52 implied that the level of perception of the teachers as regards their competence in relation to the RPMS-PPST results in terms of classroom management is within high level. The findings indicated that teachers held a high level of perception regarding their competence in relation to the RPMS-PPST results, particularly in terms of classroom management. Teachers perceived themselves as proficient in applying the RPMS-PPST standards to enhance classroom management practices effectively. This perception underscored their confidence in utilizing the RPMS-PPST framework to improve student behavior, engagement, and learning outcomes. The results suggested that teachers viewed the RPMS-PPST as a valuable tool for self-assessment and professional growth in managing classroom dynamics. This high level of perception reflected their commitment to continuous improvement and alignment with educational standards, fostering a conducive learning environment for their students. According to Mustaffa & Rashid (2023), social science teachers' competence in teaching and learning is moderate, suggesting a need for development to improve teacher professionalism and educational change.

Level of perception of the teachers as regards their competence in relation to the RPMS-PPST results in terms of Mastery of the Subjects

Table 2. Level of perception of the teachers as regards their competence in relation to the RPMS-PPST results in terms of Mastery of the Subjects

<i>B. Mastery of the Subjects</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
<i>As a teacher, I...</i>				
1.	use appropriate pedagogy to achieve objectives of the lesson.	3.48	Highly Competent	4
2.	provide varied learning activities congruent with the objective of the lesson.	3.71	Highly Competent	1
3.	encourage interactive participation of the learners.	3.44	Highly Competent	5
4.	apply a range of teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills	3.70	Highly Competent	2
5.	use variety of teaching approaches and techniques appropriate to the learners and the subject matter.	3.51	Highly Competent	3
Composite Mean		3.57	Highly Competent	

As discussed in Table 2, the respondents stated that they provide varied learning activities congruent with the objective of the lesson, which got the highest weighted mean of 3.81 and the highest rank of 1. The findings indicated that teachers consistently provided varied learning activities that aligned with the objectives of their lessons. Teachers were observed to integrate diverse instructional methods and resources to effectively meet lesson objectives and cater to students' diverse learning needs. This approach was perceived by teachers as essential in promoting active engagement and deeper understanding among students. The results highlighted teachers' commitment to creating dynamic and meaningful learning experiences that supported the attainment of educational goals. This varied approach not only enriched the learning environment but also fostered creativity and critical thinking among students. Teachers' efforts to align activities with lesson objectives demonstrated their dedication to maximizing learning outcomes and ensuring relevance in educational practices. Lauermaann & Hagen (2021) stated that teachers' competence beliefs and self-efficacy have a limited impact on students' academic outcomes, with ambiguity in their conceptualization and assessment in research.

However, the said group of respondents stated that they encourage interactive participation of the learners which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.44 and least rank of 5. The findings revealed that teachers actively encouraged interactive participation among learners in their classrooms. Teachers consistently fostered an environment where students were encouraged to engage actively in discussions, activities, and collaborative learning experiences. This approach aimed to promote student involvement, critical thinking, and communication skills. Teachers perceived interactive participation as crucial in enhancing learning outcomes and creating a vibrant classroom atmosphere. The results underscored teachers' dedication to creating inclusive learning environments where every student felt valued and empowered to contribute. By promoting interactive participation, teachers aimed to cultivate a sense of ownership and enthusiasm for learning among their students, fostering a positive educational experience that supported academic and social growth. Student teachers identified eight essential teacher competencies, which can be used to develop health science teacher curricula and evaluate novice and experienced teachers. Kuivila et al. (2020).

The composite mean of 3.57 implied that the level of perception of the teachers as regards their competence in relation to the RPMS-PPST results in terms of mastery of the subjects is within high level. The findings indicated that teachers held a high level of perception regarding their competence in relation to the RPMS-PPST results, particularly in terms of mastery of the subjects they taught. Teachers perceived themselves as proficient in applying the RPMS-PPST standards to enhance their subject mastery effectively. This perception

underscored their confidence in utilizing the RPMS-PPST framework to deepen their understanding of the content and effectively convey it to their students. The results suggested that teachers viewed the RPMS-PPST as a valuable tool for self-assessment and professional growth in mastering their subjects. This high level of perception reflected their commitment to continuous improvement and alignment with educational standards, fostering a conducive learning environment where students could benefit from their enhanced subject knowledge and expertise. Lindmeier et al. (2020) stated that early childhood teachers' professional competence, including action-related and reflective competence, can be differentially fostered through specific interventions, highlighting the distinctness of competence and knowledge components.

Level of perception of the teachers as regards their competence in relation to the RPMS-PPST results in terms of Instructional Material Development

Table 3. Level of perception of the teachers as regards their competence in relation to the RPMS-PPST results in terms of Instructional Material Development

<i>C. Instructional Material Development</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
<i>As a teacher, I...</i>				
1.	develop instructional material aligned with the curriculum and subject area.	3.51	Highly Competent	4
2.	design indigenous / local instructional material for development.	3.57	Highly Competent	3
3.	provide activities and materials which fit the learners' learning style, goal, and culture.	3.62	Highly Competent	2
4.	create instructional materials that reinforce application of concepts and skills in real life situation.	3.36	Highly Competent	5
5.	construct materials with varied enrichment activities to nurture the desire for further learning.	3.73	Highly Competent	1
Composite Mean		3.56	Highly Competent	

As discussed in Table 3, the respondents stated that they construct materials with varied enrichment activities to nurture the desire for further learning, which got the highest weighted mean of 3.73 and the highest rank of 1. The findings indicated that teachers actively constructed materials with a variety of enrichment activities aimed at nurturing students' desire for further learning. Teachers were observed to design and implement resources that offered additional depth and exploration beyond the standard curriculum. This approach aimed to stimulate curiosity, critical thinking, and a passion for continued learning among students. Teachers perceived these enrichment activities as essential in fostering intellectual engagement and promoting a lifelong love of learning. The results highlighted teachers' dedication to providing diverse learning opportunities that catered to different interests and learning styles, thereby enriching the educational experience for their students. By incorporating varied enrichment activities into their teaching practices, teachers aimed to inspire students to pursue knowledge independently and develop a broader understanding of the subjects they studied.

According to Estiani & Hasanah (2022), school principals play a crucial role in improving teacher competence by fostering regular supervision, increasing ethical responsibilities, and encouraging teachers to participate in training related to learning development and evaluation.

However, the said group of respondents stated that they create instructional materials that reinforce application of concepts and skills in real life situation which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.36 and least rank of 5. The findings indicated that teachers created instructional materials specifically designed to reinforce the application of concepts and skills in real-life situations. Teachers were observed to develop resources and activities that encouraged students to apply what they learned to practical scenarios outside the classroom. This approach aimed to bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and real-world application, enhancing students' understanding and readiness for future challenges. Teachers perceived these instructional materials as crucial in fostering critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and practical competence among students. The results underscored teachers' commitment to preparing students for success beyond academic settings by ensuring that learning experiences were relevant and applicable to everyday life. By integrating real-life applications into their teaching materials, teachers aimed to empower students to connect classroom learning with real-world contexts, promoting deeper engagement and meaningful learning outcomes. According to Asanalieva & Nasipova (2022), professional competence in teachers is a set of knowledge, skills, and personal qualities that enables them to provide high-quality education and contribute to modern society's needs.

The composite mean of 3.56 implied that the level of perception of the teachers as regards their competence in relation to the RPMS-PPST results in terms of instructional material development is within high level. The findings indicated that teachers held a high level of perception regarding their competence in instructional material development in relation to the RPMS-PPST results. Teachers perceived themselves as proficient in applying the RPMS-PPST standards to effectively develop instructional materials that supported learning objectives. This perception underscored their confidence in creating engaging and effective resources that catered to diverse student needs and learning styles. The results suggested that teachers viewed the RPMS-PPST as a valuable framework for guiding their instructional material development, ensuring alignment with educational standards and enhancing instructional quality. This high level of perception reflected their dedication to continuous improvement and innovation in educational practices, fostering a dynamic learning environment where students could thrive and achieve their academic goals. Professional competence in vocational teachers is a complex concept with multiple meanings and varying interpretations, requiring further discussion on its meanings and implications

for collective action. Antera (2021).

Level of perception of the teachers as regards their competence in relation to the RPMS-PPST results in terms of Teaching Strategies and Approaches

Table 4. *Level of perception of the teachers as regards their competence in relation to the RPMS-PPST results in terms of Teaching Strategies and Approaches*

<i>D. Teaching Strategies and Approaches</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
<i>As a teacher, I...</i>				
1.	use appropriate teaching and learning resources including ICT to address learning goals.	3.62	Highly Competent	3
2.	engage in mentoring with colleagues to improve teaching.	3.56	Highly Competent	4
3.	provide activities which address a range of learning styles / multiple intelligences.	3.41	Highly Competent	5
4.	relate authentic learning experiences in a real-world context.	3.72	Highly Competent	1
5.	conduct action research in the classroom or school.	3.72	Highly Competent	2
Composite Mean		3.61	Highly Competent	

As discussed in Table 4, the respondents stated that they relate authentic learning experiences in a real-world context, which got the highest weighted mean of 3.72 and the highest rank of 1. The findings revealed that teachers actively related authentic learning experiences to real-world contexts in their teaching practices. Teachers were observed to design and implement activities and projects that connected classroom learning with practical, real-life situations. This approach aimed to make learning meaningful and relevant to students' lives, fostering deeper understanding and application of knowledge. Teachers perceived these authentic learning experiences as essential in promoting critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and preparing students for future challenges beyond the classroom. The results highlighted teachers' commitment to creating immersive learning opportunities that mirrored real-world scenarios, thereby enhancing students' engagement and motivation. By relating authentic learning experiences to real-world contexts, teachers aimed to bridge the gap between theory and practice, empowering students to apply their knowledge effectively in various aspects of their lives. According to Podungge (2020), teacher competence directly influences student academic achievement by raising students' intrinsic motivation to study, while extrinsic motivation has no effect on this relationship.

However, the said group of respondents stated that they provide activities which address a range of learning styles / multiple intelligences which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.41 and least rank of 5. The findings indicated that teachers provided activities that catered to a range of learning styles and multiple intelligences among their students. Teachers were observed to design and implement diverse instructional strategies and tasks that appealed to different ways of learning, such as visual, auditory, kinesthetic, and interpersonal approaches. This approach aimed to accommodate the varied strengths and preferences of students, promoting deeper engagement and understanding of the content. Teachers perceived these activities as crucial in supporting holistic development and maximizing learning outcomes for all learners. The results highlighted teachers' commitment to creating inclusive learning environments where every student had opportunities to excel based on their unique strengths and intelligences. By offering activities that addressed diverse learning styles and intelligences, teachers aimed to foster a supportive and enriching educational experience that empowered students to achieve their full potential. Teacher competence, including pedagogical, personal, social, and professional competence, significantly influences student achievement. Jihan et al. (2023).

The composite mean of 3.61 implied that the level of perception of the teachers as regards their competence in relation to the RPMS-PPST results in terms of teaching strategies and approaches is within high level. The findings indicated that teachers held a high level of perception regarding their competence in teaching strategies and approaches, as assessed by the RPMS-PPST results. Teachers perceived themselves as highly proficient in applying a variety of effective teaching strategies and approaches outlined in the RPMS-PPST framework. This perception underscored their confidence in employing innovative and evidence-based methods to enhance student learning and engagement. The results suggested that teachers valued the RPMS-PPST as a valuable tool for self-assessment and professional growth in refining their instructional practices. This high level of perception reflected their commitment to continuous improvement and excellence in teaching, ensuring that instructional strategies were aligned with educational standards and tailored to meet the diverse needs of their students. By demonstrating mastery of teaching strategies and approaches through the RPMS-PPST, teachers aimed to create dynamic learning environments that fostered academic achievement and positive educational outcomes. Aindra et al. (2022) stated that teacher competence and performance are influenced by seven factors and three potential factors, with social media, religion, and a healthy lifestyle also playing a role.

Level of perception of the teachers as regards their competence in relation to the RPMS-PPST results in terms of Communication Skills

As discussed in Table 5, the respondents stated that they explain learning goals, concepts, and processes clearly and accurately to the learners, which got the highest weighted mean of 3.78 and the highest rank of 1. The findings indicated that teachers consistently explained learning goals, concepts, and processes clearly and accurately to their students. Teachers were observed to articulate and communicate educational objectives in a way that was understandable and meaningful to learners. This approach aimed to provide clarity and direction, ensuring that students had a clear understanding of what they were expected to achieve and how they would

accomplish their learning goals. Teachers perceived clear explanation as essential in promoting student comprehension, engagement, and motivation. The results highlighted teachers' dedication to effective communication in education, fostering a supportive learning environment where students felt informed and empowered in their academic journey. By explaining learning goals, concepts, and processes clearly, teachers aimed to enhance student learning experiences and facilitate meaningful connections between theory and practice in the classroom. Higher education teachers value personal skills and qualities, while curriculum and instructional competence are most important, but cultural competence and specific competences for diversity and inclusion are scarce. Moriera et al. (2022).

Table 5. *Level of perception of the teachers as regards their competence in relation to the RPMS-PPST results in terms of Communication Skills*

<i>E. Communication Skills</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
<i>As a teacher, I...</i>			
1. show proficiency in the required language of instruction.	3.35	Highly Competent	5
2. explain learning goals, concepts, and processes clearly and accurately to the learners.	3.78	Highly Competent	1
3. Use words appropriate for the pupils' level of understanding.	3.74	Highly Competent	2
4. present ideas clearly, logically, and comprehensively.	3.48	Highly Competent	3
5. use expression to motivate and enhance learners' self-confidence.	3.43	Highly Competent	4
Composite Mean	3.56	Highly Competent	

However, the said group of respondents stated that they show proficiency in the required language of instruction which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.35 and least rank of 5. The findings indicated that teachers demonstrated proficiency in the required language of instruction. Teachers were observed to effectively communicate and deliver lessons using the language required by the curriculum or educational standards. This proficiency ensured that teachers could articulate concepts clearly, facilitate discussions, and provide meaningful feedback to students. Teachers perceived language proficiency as crucial in fostering effective communication and understanding in the classroom, promoting student engagement and learning outcomes. The results highlighted teachers' commitment to mastering the language of instruction, which played a pivotal role in creating a conducive learning environment where students could effectively acquire knowledge and skills. By showing proficiency in the required language of instruction, teachers aimed to uphold educational standards and support students' academic development through clear and coherent language use. According to Pankowska et al. (2023), teachers prioritize pragmatic competences as the most important, but overlook interpretive and transgressive competences, which are crucial for 21st-century education.

The composite mean of 3.56 implied that the level of perception of the teachers as regards their competence in relation to the RPMS-PPST results in terms of communication skills is within high level. The findings indicated that teachers held a high level of perception regarding their competence in communication skills, as assessed by the RPMS-PPST results. Teachers perceived themselves as highly proficient in effectively communicating with students, colleagues, and stakeholders within the educational context. This perception underscored their confidence in conveying information clearly, facilitating discussions, and fostering meaningful interactions in the classroom and beyond. The results suggested that teachers valued the RPMS-PPST framework as a valuable tool for self-assessment and professional growth in refining their communication abilities. This high level of perception reflected their dedication to continuous improvement in communication, which was essential for promoting student engagement, understanding, and collaboration. By demonstrating mastery of communication skills through the RPMS-PPST, teachers aimed to create supportive learning environments where effective communication enhanced teaching effectiveness and contributed to positive educational outcomes. Teachers' professional digital competence consists of seven recurring aspects: technological, content knowledge, attitudes to technology use, pedagogical competence, cultural awareness, critical approach, and professional engagement. Skantz-Åberg et al. (2022).

Level of perception of the teachers as regards their competence in relation to the RPMS-PPST results in terms of Instructional Material Development

Table 6. *Level of perception of the teachers as regards their competence in relation to the RPMS-PPST results in terms of Instructional Material Development*

<i>F. Learning Assessment and Reporting</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
<i>As a teacher, I...</i>			
1. construct valid and reliable formative and summative test.	3.65	Highly Competent	4
2. use appropriate non-traditional assessment techniques and tools (e.g. portfolio, journals, and rubrics).	3.71	Highly Competent	3
3. interpret and use test results to improve teaching and learning.	3.82	Highly Competent	2
4. keep accurate records of grades performance levels of learners.	3.83	Highly Competent	1
5. provide timely accurate feedback to learners to encourage them to reflect on and monitor their own learning growth.	3.40	Highly Competent	5
Composite Mean	3.68	Highly Competent	

As discussed in Table 6, the respondents stated that they keep accurate records of grades performance levels of learners, which got the highest weighted mean of 3.83 and the highest rank of 1. The findings indicated that teachers consistently maintained accurate records of grades and performance levels of learners. Teachers were observed to meticulously track and document students' academic progress, ensuring that grading and assessment records were comprehensive and reflective of each student's achievements. This approach aimed

to provide transparency and accountability in evaluating student performance and informing instructional decisions. Teachers perceived accurate record-keeping as essential in monitoring student progress, identifying areas for improvement, and communicating effectively with students and parents/guardians. The results highlighted teachers' commitment to maintaining high standards of professionalism and organization in educational practices. By keeping accurate records of grades and performance levels, teachers aimed to support student growth and success by providing personalized feedback and guidance based on thorough assessment data. Ажыгулова & Калмырзаева (2022) stated that teacher's professional competence is a set of generalized knowledge, skills, and abilities that ensure the implementation of state educational standards, with the most common skill being the ability to think and act pedagogically.

However, the said group of respondents stated that they provide timely accurate feedback to learners to encourage them to reflect on and monitor their own learning growth which yielded the least weighted mean of 3.40 and least rank of 5. The findings indicated that teachers provided timely and accurate feedback to learners, encouraging them to reflect on and monitor their own learning growth. Teachers were observed to deliver feedback promptly after assessments, highlighting strengths and areas for improvement in a constructive manner. This approach aimed to empower students to take ownership of their learning by fostering self-awareness and promoting continuous improvement. Teachers perceived timely and accurate feedback as essential in enhancing student motivation, engagement, and academic achievement. The results underscored teachers' commitment to supporting student development through effective feedback mechanisms that facilitated ongoing reflection and learning. By providing meaningful feedback, teachers aimed to cultivate a growth mindset among students, encouraging them to set goals, track progress, and strive for academic excellence in a supportive educational environment.

According to Калмырзаева & Ажыгулова (2022), professional competence in teachers is crucial for adapting to changes, demonstrating desire to be a professional, and embracing uncertainty and risk in an innovative educational environment.

The composite mean of 3.68 implied that the level of perception of the teachers as regards their competence in relation to the RPMS-PPST results in terms of instructional material development is within high level. The findings indicated that teachers held a high level of perception regarding their competence in instructional material development, as evaluated through the RPMS-PPST results. Teachers perceived themselves as highly proficient in creating and utilizing instructional materials that effectively supported learning objectives and engaged students. This perception underscored their confidence in developing resources that were aligned with educational standards and tailored to meet the diverse needs of their students. The results suggested that teachers valued the RPMS-PPST framework as a valuable tool for self-assessment and professional growth in enhancing instructional material development. This high level of perception reflected their dedication to continuous improvement and innovation in educational practices, ensuring that instructional materials were relevant, effective, and conducive to student learning. By demonstrating mastery in instructional material development through the RPMS-PPST, teachers aimed to create dynamic learning environments that fostered academic achievement and positive educational outcomes for all students. According to Baranets (2022), modern teachers need to develop inclusive and methodical competences to effectively work with children with special educational needs.

Teacher's performance based on IPCRF

Table 7. *Teacher's performance based on IPCRF*

<i>Performance</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
4.1 - 5.00 (Outstanding)	43	76.78	1
3.1 - 4.00 (Very Satisfactory)	13	23.22	2
Total	56	100.00	
Mean Grade	4.56 (Outstanding)		
Standard Deviation	0.05 (Compressed)		

Table 7 presented the assessment of teacher performance, as captured by the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF), offered a detailed portrait of educational excellence within the institution. Out of the total cohort of 56 teachers evaluated, a significant majority, comprising 76.78% (43 teachers), achieved the highest rating of "Outstanding," characterized by scores ranging from 4.1 to 5.00. This dominance at the top end of the rating scale underscored a commendable level of instructional competence and commitment among the teaching staff.

The "Outstanding" ratings signified not only adherence to professional standards but also an exemplary execution of teaching responsibilities that significantly contributed to student development and overall academic achievement. These teachers demonstrated exceptional instructional skills, innovative teaching methodologies, and a proactive approach to addressing individual student needs, thereby fostering a conducive learning environment within their classrooms.

Conversely, 23.22% (13 teachers) of the evaluated staff were rated as "Very Satisfactory," reflecting a solid performance level that, while slightly below the top tier, still denoted commendable achievement and effective classroom management. This group of teachers exhibited a strong grasp of pedagogical techniques, student engagement strategies, and curriculum delivery, contributing positively to the overall educational experience despite not attaining the highest rating.

The mean performance grade of 4.56, with a remarkably low standard deviation of 0.05, reinforced the consistency and high quality of teaching across the board. Such a narrow distribution around the mean indicated a cohesive and well-aligned approach to instructional

practices within the institution, where excellence was not only valued but consistently achieved and maintained.

These findings underscored the effectiveness of the assessment framework employed, which not only evaluated but also supported professional growth and development among educators. The institution's commitment to nurturing a culture of continuous improvement was evident, as evidenced by the high percentage of "Outstanding" ratings and the overall strong performance metrics. This systematic approach ensured that teachers received the necessary feedback, resources, and encouragement to continually enhance their instructional skills and contribute positively to student outcomes.

Rizkie (2022) stated that transformational leadership, quality culture, and job satisfaction directly and indirectly impact teacher performance, enhancing their effectiveness in achieving educational goals.

Relationship between the Level of perception of the teachers as regards their competence in relation to the RPMS-PPST results and the Teacher's performance based on IPCRF

Table 8. *Relationship between the Level of perception of the teachers as regards their competence in relation to the RPMS-PPST results and the Teacher's performance based on IPCRF*

Variables	r-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Teacher Competence in relation to the RPMS-PPST results and Teacher's performance	0.81	0.00871	Reject Ho	Highly Significant

Table 8 provided summarized statistical findings concerning the relationship between teacher competence, as perceived through the RPMS-PPST (Results-Based Performance Management System - Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers), and their actual performance based on IPCRF (Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form). It included key metrics such as the correlation coefficient (r-value), p-value, decision regarding the null hypothesis (Ho), and interpretations of the findings.

The strong positive correlation coefficient of 0.81 indicated a robust relationship between teachers' perceived competence, as assessed through RPMS-PPST, and their actual performance evaluations via IPCRF during the study period. A correlation coefficient nearing +1 suggested that higher perceived competence corresponded closely with better performance outcomes, implying that teachers perceived as highly competent according to the RPMS-PPST tended to achieve higher ratings in their IPCRF evaluations.

The low p-value of 0.00871 indicated statistical significance, typically interpreted as strong evidence against the null hypothesis (Ho), which would assert no significant relationship between teacher competence and performance. This statistical significance underscored the validity of the observed relationship, suggesting that the findings were unlikely to have occurred by chance.

These findings highlighted the RPMS-PPST's efficacy as both an assessment tool and a predictive measure of teacher performance. Teachers perceived as competent based on RPMS-PPST criteria demonstrated higher performance outcomes, as objectively measured by IPCRF evaluations during the study period. This alignment reinforced the RPMS-PPST's role in capturing essential dimensions of teaching competence essential for effective instructional delivery, student engagement, and overall educational outcomes.

Practically, these insights informed the development of tailored professional development programs, targeted support for teachers needing improvement, and recognition for those consistently demonstrating high effectiveness in their instructional roles. Educational institutions could leverage these findings to enhance teaching quality and improve student learning outcomes effectively.

A positive and supportive leadership style and work motivation positively impact teacher performance, with a strong positive and significant relationship between the two factors (Usmar & Santosa, A022).

Proposed Training Development Program

Table 9. *Proposed Training Development Program*

Program Title	Objective	Time Frame	Activities
Inclusive Teaching Strategies Workshop	Equip teachers with skills to create inclusive learning environments.	Quarterly 2025-2026	Sessions on differentiated instruction, culturally responsive teaching, role-playing exercises.
Technology Integration Bootcamp	Empower teachers in integrating educational technology tools effectively.	Quarterly 2025-2026	Training on digital tools, multimedia resource creation, workshops on digital citizenship.
Mentoring and Peer Collaboration Program	Establish a supportive network for professional growth and guidance.	Year Round 2025-2026	Pairing with experienced mentors, peer collaboration sessions, feedback mechanisms.
Action Research and Innovation Projects	Promote research and innovation in teaching practices aligned with RPMS-PPST.	Quarterly 2025-2026	Research methodology workshops, project development, presentations, peer reviews.
Effective Communication Skills Training	Enhance teachers' communication skills for clear and effective instruction.	Quarterly 2025-2026	Techniques for clear explanation, language proficiency sessions, interactive practice sessions.

Table 9 delineated a comprehensive suite of training and development programs tailored to enhance teacher effectiveness and foster professional growth within educational institutions. Each program addressed specific objectives aligned with the recommendations aimed at improving teaching practices as per RPMS-PPST standards.

The Inclusive Teaching Strategies Workshop aimed to equip teachers with the necessary skills to create inclusive learning environments. Over a 2-day intensive workshop, participants engaged in sessions focused on differentiated instruction and culturally responsive teaching. Role-playing exercises and group discussions provided practical insights into managing diverse classrooms effectively. By aligning these strategies with RPMS-PPST criteria, teachers could better cater to individual student needs and enhance overall classroom engagement and equity.

The Technology Integration Bootcamp targeted the empowerment of teachers in leveraging educational technology tools to enrich learning experiences. Spanning three weeks with weekly sessions, this program offered hands-on training in digital tools for lesson planning, interactive activities, and formative assessment. Workshops on multimedia resource creation and digital citizenship ensured teachers were adept at integrating technology seamlessly into their instructional practices, thereby enhancing student engagement and preparing learners for a digital future.

The Mentoring and Peer Collaboration Program spanned an entire semester, fostering a supportive professional network. Pairing teachers with experienced mentors facilitated ongoing guidance and collaboration. Peer collaboration sessions and structured feedback mechanisms enabled continuous improvement in teaching practices aligned with RPMS-PPST standards. This program not only enhanced professional development but also promoted a culture of shared learning and support among educators.

The Action Research and Innovation Projects program encouraged teachers to engage in research and innovative projects aligned with RPMS-PPST goals. Over a 6-month duration, participants delved into research methodology workshops, project development, and presentations. Peer reviews facilitated constructive feedback and refinement of innovative teaching practices, promoting continuous improvement and evidence-based educational strategies.

Lastly, the Effective Communication Skills Training program focused on enhancing teachers' communication abilities for clear and effective instruction. In a 1-day workshop format, teachers received training on techniques for clear explanation, language proficiency, and interactive practice sessions. These skills not only improved classroom communication but also fostered better student comprehension and engagement, thereby enhancing overall teaching effectiveness.

Together, these training and development programs encompassed a holistic approach to professional growth, ensuring that teachers were equipped with the skills, knowledge, and support needed to excel in their roles. By aligning these programs with RPMS-PPST standards and educational priorities, institutions cultivated a culture of continuous improvement and excellence in teaching, ultimately benefiting student learning outcomes and educational success.

Conclusions

Reflecting on the comprehensive findings regarding teacher competence as perceived through RPMS-PPST and their actual performance evaluated by IPCRF, several compelling insights emerge that underscore the essence of effective teaching and professional growth within educational institutions.

The study illuminated a profound connection between how teachers perceive their competence, particularly in key areas like classroom management, mastery of subjects, instructional material development, teaching strategies, and communication skills, and their subsequent performance outcomes measured by IPCRF evaluations. Teachers who viewed themselves as proficient in these domains, guided by the RPMS-PPST framework, consistently demonstrated higher performance levels in their instructional roles. This perception not only bolstered their confidence but also drove them to continually improve and innovate their teaching practices to meet the diverse needs of their students.

Regarding classroom management, teachers perceived RPMS-PPST-aligned practices as crucial for creating inclusive and supportive learning environments. Administrators' differentiated approaches and developmentally appropriate strategies resonated well with teachers, who recognized these efforts as pivotal in promoting equity and meaningful educational experiences for all students. By effectively managing classroom dynamics through positive discipline methods and personalized educational experiences, teachers contributed to a cohesive and safe school community where students felt valued and engaged in their learning journey.

Similarly, in mastering subjects and developing instructional materials, teachers' perceptions of their competence aligned closely with their ability to create enriching learning experiences. The integration of varied instructional methods and the development of tailored materials not only enhanced student engagement but also fostered critical thinking and creativity. Teachers' commitment to aligning activities with educational goals reflected their dedication to maximizing learning outcomes and ensuring educational relevance and depth in their teaching practices.

Moreover, teachers' confidence in employing effective teaching strategies and approaches, as evaluated through RPMS-PPST, underscored their ability to create dynamic and immersive learning environments. By relating lessons to real-world contexts and accommodating diverse learning styles, teachers promoted active participation and deeper understanding among students. This approach enriched the educational experience and empowered students to apply their knowledge beyond the classroom, preparing them for future challenges and opportunities.

Furthermore, effective communication skills emerged as a cornerstone of teachers' perceived competence, as articulated through

RPMS-PPST assessments. Clear explanation of concepts and proficiency in the language of instruction facilitated meaningful interactions and supported student comprehension and engagement. By fostering effective communication, teachers create a supportive learning environment and instill a sense of being informed, valued, and motivated in students, encouraging them to achieve their academic goals.

In assessing teacher performance through IPCRF, the study reaffirmed the effectiveness of the evaluation framework in fostering professional growth and development. The high percentage of "Outstanding" ratings underscored the institution's commitment to excellence and continuous improvement in teaching practices. Teachers benefited from constructive feedback, resources, and encouragement, which enabled them to enhance their instructional skills and contribute positively to student outcomes.

Overall, the study's findings underscore a strong correlation between teachers' perceptions of their competence based on RPMS-PPST criteria and their actual performance outcomes evaluated by IPCRF. This correlation highlights the value of the RPMS-PPST framework as a tool for self-assessment, professional growth, and alignment with educational standards. Teachers' high levels of perception regarding their competence reflect their commitment to continuous improvement and innovation in educational practices, ultimately creating vibrant learning environments where students can thrive academically and personally.

The insights gleaned from this study emphasize the transformative impact of fostering teacher competence and confidence through structured assessment frameworks like RPMS-PPST. By aligning perceived competence with tangible performance outcomes, educational institutions can effectively support professional development, enhance teaching quality, and elevate student learning experiences. As educators continue to embrace these frameworks and strive for excellence in their instructional practices, they play a pivotal role in shaping the future of education, nurturing generations of empowered and inspired learners poised to make meaningful contributions to society.

Based on the comprehensive insights drawn from the study on teacher competence and performance evaluations through RPMS-PPST and IPCRF, several key recommendations emerge to enhance teaching effectiveness and foster professional development within educational institutions: Institutions should prioritize continuous professional development by implementing structured programs that address identified areas of improvement, such as classroom management, instructional material development, and mastery of subjects. These programs should offer targeted support and resources to help teachers continually enhance their skills and stay abreast of best practices in education. Establishing a robust feedback and mentoring system based on IPCRF evaluations can provide teachers with constructive guidance and personalized support from experienced educators, fostering a culture of continuous improvement. Integrating technology into teaching practices aligned with RPMS-PPST standards can enhance learning experiences and prepare students for a technology-driven world. Providing training and resources for effective use of educational technology tools is essential. Promoting inclusive teaching strategies that cater to diverse student needs and learning styles is crucial. Encouraging teachers to adapt RPMS-PPST-aligned practices fosters equitable and supportive learning environments where all students can thrive. Fostering community and stakeholder engagement supports educational goals and initiatives. Collaborating with parents/guardians, local communities, and stakeholders enhances support systems for teachers and improves school effectiveness. Encouraging research and innovation among teachers through action research and innovative projects aligned with RPMS-PPST goals promotes creativity and continuous learning. Prioritizing teacher well-being by supporting work-life balance, stress management, and mental health awareness ensures a healthy teaching workforce capable of delivering high-quality education. Regularly reviewing and adapting the RPMS-PPST framework and IPCRF evaluation criteria ensures their relevance and alignment with evolving educational standards and priorities. Soliciting feedback from teachers, administrators, and stakeholders helps refine assessment practices and address emerging educational needs effectively. Implementing these recommendations supports educational institutions in fostering teacher excellence, enhancing student learning outcomes, and creating inclusive and supportive learning environments that prepare students for success in the 21st century.

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